

MEDICAL SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING MYELODYSPLASTIC SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

A rare clinical case report is provided regarding an 83-year-old man who was admitted to the Hematology Department of the First University Clinic of Tbilisi State Medical University (Georgia) in 2021. The patient was scheduled for surgical treatment due to cataract. The patient did not have any symptoms of Fanconi anemia until the age of 80. The preoperative complete blood count revealed leukopenia, neutropenia: leukocyte - $2.6 \times 10^9/l$; neutrophil - 22%. General condition satisfactory, constitutional type - normosthenic. He does not tolerate alcohol and does not use tobacco. He had no genetic history. There are no developmental defects. This case suggests that myelodysplastic syndrome is multisymptomatic and therefore, determining the underlying causes is crucial. Fanconi anemia, as known, is homozygous, while this case, which has been confirmed as heterozygous, supports the idea that it may transform into myelodysplasia over time. This gives us grounds to conclude that it is advisable to conduct a thorough examination of all cytopenic patients, including from a molecular-genetic perspective.

Keywords: Fanconi Anemia, Myelodysplastic Syndrome, Bone Marrow Report.

Fanconi anemia is a rare genetic disease, also known as Fanconi congenital panmyelopathy. It often occurs in consanguineous marriages. It is transmitted in an autosomal recessive manner. It is characterized by impaired hematopoiesis, developmental defects, and the formation of malignant tumors. It is manifested by pallor, weakness, frequent bleeding, and bruising under the skin. In general, a special system of enzymes in cells, under the influence of chemical and physical reagents or during the biosynthesis process, restores the broken DNA molecule. In Fanconi anemia, a genetic defect in a cluster of proteins responsible for DNA repair leads to increased chromosome fragility. As a result, bone marrow dysfunction develops. In particular, neoplasia and aplastic anemia (1). Oncological diseases are often represented by acute myeloid leukemia, when the accumulation of altered white blood cells is provoked. This leads to inhibition of the growth of erythrocytes, platelets, and normal leukocytes. Accordingly, in aplastic anemia, the maturation and growth of all three types of blood cells is sharply reduced as a result of bone marrow dysplasia.

Fanconi anemia can be caused by mutations in at least 15 genes. The proteins produced by these genes are involved in a cellular process known as the FA pathway. The FA pathway is involved in DNA replication. The FA pathway sends certain proteins to the site of damage, which causes DNA to be repaired so that DNA replication can continue (2).

The FA pathway is particularly sensitive to certain types of DNA damage known as interstrand cross-links (ICLs). ICLs occur when two building blocks of DNA (nucleotides) on opposite strands of DNA are abnormally attached or linked together, stopping the process of DNA replication. ICLs can be caused by a build-up of toxic substances in the body or by treatment with certain cancer drugs (3).

Eight proteins associated with Fanconi anemia group together to form a complex known as the FA core complex. The FA core complex activates two proteins called FANCD2 and FANCI. Activation of these two proteins brings DNA repair proteins to the ICL region so that the cross-link can be removed and DNA replication can continue.

80-90 percent of Fanconi anemia cases are caused by mutations in one of three genes, FANCA, FANCC, and FANCG. These genes provide instructions for making the components of the FA core complex. Mutations in many genes associated with the FA core complex cause the complex to malfunction and disrupt the entire FA pathway. As a result, DNA damage is not repaired effectively, and over time, ICLs accumulate. ICLs stop DNA replication.

Ultimately, they lead to pathological cell death due to the inability to make new DNA molecules or to uncontrolled cell growth due to the lack of DNA repair processes. Cells that divide rapidly, such as bone marrow cells and developing fetal cells, are particularly affected. The death of these cells leads to the reduction in blood cells and the physical abnormalities characteristic of Fanconi anemia. When the accumulation of errors in DNA causes uncontrolled cell growth, acute myeloid leukemia or other cancers can develop (3).

Fanconi anemia is most often inherited in an autosomal recessive pattern, meaning that both copies of the gene in each cell have mutations. The parents of an individual with an autosomal recessive condition carry one copy of the mutated gene, but they usually do not show symptoms of the condition.

The condition is very rarely inherited in an X-linked recessive pattern. The gene for X-linked recessive Fanconi anemia is located on the X chromosome, one of the two sex chromosomes. In males (who have only one X chromosome), one altered copy of the gene

in each cell is sufficient to cause the condition. In females (who have two X chromosomes), one altered copy of the gene in each cell is sufficient to cause the condition. In females, the mutation must occur in both copies of the gene to cause the disorder. Because women are less likely to have two altered copies of this gene, males are more likely to suffer from X-linked recessive disorders than females. A characteristic of X-linked inheritance is that fathers cannot pass on X-linked traits to their sons.

People with Fanconi anemia experience fatigue due to low red blood cell counts (anemia), frequent infections due to low white blood cell counts (neutropenia), and clotting problems due to low platelet counts (thrombocytopenia); and physical developmental defects. For example:

Uneven skin color, unusually light skin (hypopigmentation or café-au-lait spots), flat spots that are darker than the surrounding skin, malformed thumbs or forearms, and other skeletal problems, and short stature. Other developmental defects of the kidneys or urinary tract; gastrointestinal disorders; heart defects; eye abnormalities, such as small or abnormally shaped eyes; and malformed ears and hearing loss. People with this condition may also have genital abnormalities or reproductive system abnormalities (4).

As a result, most affected men and about half of affected women are unable to father biological children. Additional signs and symptoms may include abnormalities of the brain and spinal cord (central nervous system), including an increase in fluid in the center of the brain (hydrocephalus), or an unusually small head size (microcephaly.)

Life expectancy in Fanconi anemia depends on the severity of bone marrow dysfunction. Sometimes patients live without treatment to about 40 years, although more often they die in early childhood from severe anemia and oncological diseases. In modern conditions, it is possible to increase life expectancy with timely allogeneic bone marrow transplantation.

An 83-year-old man applied to the Hematology Department of the First University Clinic of Tbilisi (Georgia) State Medical University in 2021. The patient was planning surgical treatment for cataracts. The patient did not have any symptoms of Fanconi anemia until the age of 80.

The preoperative general blood test revealed leukopenia, neutropenia: leukocyte - $2.6 \times 10^9/l$; neutrophil - 22 %, general condition satisfactory, constitutional type - normosthenic. Does not tolerate alcohol and does not use tobacco. Has no genetic history. No developmental defects are noted.

In 2022, the patient repeatedly applied to the hematology department, in addition to leukopenia, macrocytic anemia was observed in the general blood test. Treatment was carried out with vitamin B 12. However, leukopenia and neutropenia remained. In order to verify the cause, a trepanobiopsy of the femur was performed and a morphological study of the material was performed: the bone tissue is well represented in the trepanation and no significant changes were seen in it, the overall structure of the bone marrow is preserved, the cellular composition is polymorphic. All three branches are well represented. Against such a basic background, single hypocellular areas are noted, where the amount

of adipose tissue is increased. Due to the absence of clinically significant changes, it was decided to observe the dynamics.

During a routine check-up in 2024, the patient's blood showed changes, which led to repeated thorough studies. Namely: Bone Marrow Report, Haematological Malignancy Gene Panel Report (both studies were conducted at Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre Victoria Australia), FISH cytogenetic study, flow cytometry, Comprehensive Immune and Cytopenia Panel Plus.

Bone Marrow Report, Conclusion: The aspirate demonstrates trilineage dysplasia and a myelodysplastic neoplasm is favored (MDS-Low blasts with MLD). Correlation with clinical features, either ancillary tests (hematinic, heavy metals), and molecular/cytogenetic studies are required for diagnostic confirmation and integration (Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre Victoria Australia).

Fish cytogenetic study. Conclusion: The research findings did not confirm the presence of trisomy or monosomy of chromosomes 7 and 8, nor deletions Del(5q); 17p13 del. (TP53); Del(7q); Del(20q) in the evaluated interphase cells.

Flow cytometry, Conclusion: No changes-Comprehensive Immune and Cytopenia Panel Plus: Sequence and Del/Dup (CNV) analysis using the blueprint genetics (BpG) Comprehensive Immune and Cytopenia Panel did not detect any known disease-causing or rare variants that could explain the patient's phenotype as described to the laboratory at the time of interpretation. Summary of Results: Negative for explaining the patient's phenotype. The patient is heterozygous for FANCCD2 c.757C>T, p (Arg253), which is likely pathogenic. (Blueprint Genetics Oy, Finland).

Based on the in-depth studies conducted, it is conceivable that the cause of the patient's leukopenia and neutropenia may be related to the development of myelodysplastic disease. This case suggests that myelodysplastic syndrome is multisymptomatic, and therefore, determining the underlying causes is crucial. Fanconi anemia, as known, is homozygous, while this case, which has been confirmed as heterozygous, supports the idea that it may transform into myelodysplasia over time. This gives us grounds to conclude that it is advisable to conduct a thorough examination of all cytopenic patients, including from a molecular-genetic perspective.

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